

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Thermal Interface Materials Under Compression

The thermal conductivity of silicone and non-silicone thermal interface materials (TIMs) under different compressed states was measured using the Transient Plane Source (TPS) method.

Thermal interface materials are typically applied within the interfaces between the layers, filling in the air gaps, improving the heat transfer rate, and ensuring that waste heat is dissipated away from critical components¹. Various factors define the effectiveness of TIMs in thermal management, including the type, composition, filler distribution, and bulk thermal conductivity (k) of the materials, the quality of the interface surfaces, and the applied loading conditions. It is important to note that choosing the correct type of TIMs, thermal pads, gels, or grease is highly dependent on the application's specific needs².

Figure 1. Thermal interface material applied in electronics (Left) and Trident's FLEX Transient Plane Source (Right).

In this application note, the TPS method available on the Trident platform was used to measure the thermal conductivity of two thermal pads. The 13 mm TPS sensor was placed between two stacks of thermal pads, and the Compression Test Accessory (CTA) was used to apply the compression load. The effective thermal conductivity under differing applied loads was assessed to mimic different representative conditions of the material. The digital variance indicator, included with the CTA, was used to track the compression state (deflection% - change of sample's thickness as the compression load is applied). Reported values are the average of 3 measurements taken at room temperature.

¹ Zhang, Pei et al, Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys., 2021, 23, 753, DOI: 10.1039/d0cp05514j

² Mariatti et al, Carbon, 2020, 168, 65-112, DOI: 10.1016/j.carbon.2020.06.012

Figure 2. Thermal conductivity of silicone (Left) and non-silicone (Right) TIMs under varying compressed states.

As shown in Figure , when no compression load is applied to the Silicone TIM, the thermal conductivity was measured to be 8.59 W/mK. Increasing applied compression load increases this to 9.34 W/mK at 20% deflection (8.7% increase). The thermal conductivity was measured to be 9.93 W/mK at 45% deflection (6.3% increase). The non-silicone thermal gap exhibited an initial 16.4% increase when deflection increased from 0% to 20%, followed by a 23.2% increase at 45% deflection. Although the Non-Silicone TIM exhibited an overall lower bulk thermal conductivity, the percent increase was much more significant when subjected to varying compressive loads.

In summary, the thermal conductivity of thermal interface materials under varying compressed states was measured using the Trident's FLEX TPS with the Compression Test Accessory (CTA). This study demonstrates the FLEX TPS's capability to measure the change in thermal conductivity of thermal interface materials under expected working conditions.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident thermal conductivity instrument, visit www.TridentThermalConductivity.com